

D7.2 Test Protocols/Reports of the Performed Tests

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Deliverable Information sheet

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Executive summary

This deliverable includes:

- A summary of the executed MARBEL test procedures at all assembly levels: cell, module, pack
- Each test procedure is documented with results, the evaluation procedure and observed problems / reworks
- For each performed test, an evaluation and summary were done to assess the achievement of the intended goals / intended outcomes of the test

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List of abbreviations

AI	<i>Artificial Intelligence</i>
BMS	<i>Battery Management System</i>
BOL	<i>Begin of Life</i>
BP	<i>Battery Pack</i>
CAN	<i>Controller Area Network</i>
CC	<i>Constant Current</i>
CC/CV	<i>Constant Current / Constant Voltage</i>
DC	<i>Direct Current</i>
DUT	<i>Device Under Test</i>
ECM	<i>Equivalent Circuit Model</i>
eVIL	<i>Electric Vehicle in the Loop</i>
HPPC	<i>Hybrid Pulse Power Characterization</i>
HV	<i>High Voltage</i>
iSCM	<i>Integrated Smart Cell Manager</i>
KPI	<i>Key Performance Indicator</i>
NMC	<i>Nickel Manganese Cobalt</i>
OCV	<i>Open Circuit Voltage</i>
PCB	<i>Printed Circuit Board</i>
RC	<i>Resistance/Capacitance</i>
RESS	<i>Rechargeable Energy Storage System</i>
RL	<i>Reinforcement Learning</i>
SAE	<i>Society of Automotive Engineers</i>
SOC	<i>State of Charge</i>
TR	<i>Thermal Runaway</i>
WLTC	<i>Worldwide Harmonized Light Vehicle Test Procedure / Cycle</i>

Introduction

This deliverable *D7.2 Test Protocols/Reports of the Performed Tests* presents the implementation and results of the tests at cell, module and pack level. The planning of these tests is recorded in Deliverable *D7.1 Definition of Test Procedures as a Protocol*, where a thorough description of the intended setups and profiles had been made. The results obtained are evaluated for each test and the most important findings are summarized.

This document reflects the ambition of the MARBEL project: after developing, planning and assembling the modules and packs, they are now tested for their performance under conditions within the normal operating range and their behavior under conditions outside the normal operating range, as well as during 2nd-Life, considering the complete life cycle of the developed MARBEL system. This considers the individual components of the modules and packs, as well as the interaction between the individual components, such as the sensors, software, and actors. It is of interest how different conditions affect cycling, how the cooling system performs, or how the pack behaves during a thermal runaway of a single cell.

Thus, any available entity to be tested was considered in the whole testing activities in MARBEL. With these tests, not only the performance and safety of the MARBEL modules and battery packs can be validated and benchmarked, but valuable insights for conducting future tests at all assembly levels (cell, module and pack) are also gained. These insights will help to reduce resources such as time and money required for such tests in the future.

1. Results of tests related to performance demonstration

1.1. Cell level

The cells used in the MARBEL system had initially been characterized to get the main parameters. The basic tests therefore had been applied in an isolated manner at the beginning, but also in combination with other tests where necessary (e.g. standard cycle before WLTC cycling).

1.1.1. Initial standard cycle / "formation"

Figure 1: Flowchart "standard cycle" to deduce nominal capacity @ C/3 [A].

Figure 2: Formation cycles at the very beginning of the tests; current (red) and voltage (green).

The formation cycles show the typical voltage range and curve shape for NMC cells. The results also show the standard capacity of the cells at C/3 A in line with the manufacturer's information.

1.1.2. Quasi-OCV curve measurement

Figure 3: Flowchart of "quasi-OCV" measurement @C/20 [A].

As mentioned in D7.1, the quasi-OCV curve was measured using a very low current of C/20 for both the charge and discharge direction. To ensure that the cell is fully charged/discharged, a two-step CV-phase had been applied before the continuous low-current OCV measurement was started.

Figure 4: Complete measurement of quasi-charge/discharge OCV curve; current (red) and voltage (green).

Comparing the charge and discharge OCV, a hysteresis is observable:

Table 1: SOC-quasi-OCV-curve values for charge and discharge direction.

SOC / %	OCV_charge / V	OCV_discharge / V
0	2.917	2.752
10	3.519	3.486
20	3.595	3.558
30	3.655	3.616
40	3.686	3.660
50	3.740	3.703
60	3.821	3.786
70	3.944	3.914
80	4.059	4.035
90	4.175	4.148
100	4.301	4.285

Figure 5: quasi-OCV-curve showing hysteresis between charge and discharge direction.

The following figures show the comparison between different tested cells.

Figure 6: qOCV test: Voltage (V) during charging vs SOC (%) comparison for the different cells.

Figure 7: qOCV Test: Voltage (V) during discharging vs SOC (%) comparison for the different cells.

1.1.3. Rate capability at different C-rates

Figure 8: Flowchart of "rate capability" test @ C/3 - 1C [A].

The results from the capacity validation test are used to deduce the reduction of capacity at higher C-rates. Especially when it comes to demanding driving cycles like WLTC, it is a crucial information.

Figure 9: Capacity validation cycle at C/2 and 1C discharge current; current (red) and voltage (green).

In the shown figure, the C/3 A discharge rate has not been applied, since it was part of the initial formation cycles. However, an additional test to deduce the discharge capacity at 2C was done:

Figure 10: Discharge capacity test at 2C; current (red) and voltage (green).

1.1.4. HPPC test

Figure 11: Flowchart of HPPC-test; a profile that applies current pulses to measure voltage response.

The main purpose of the HPPC test is to deduce parameters like the internal resistance and power capability of the cell. The test has been used to characterize the cell's ECM model parameters in general, but also to monitor them over the lifetime of the cells. For the latter, the HPPC tests has been applied in between cycle rounds, whereas the calculated parameters then reflect a potential change due to degradation.

Figure 12: Full HPPC test sequence with pulses applied to the cell at different SOC steps, current (red) and voltage (green).

The applied pulse sequences consist of a charge and a discharge pulse, which causes the cell voltage to rise or drop. This voltage response together with the applied current pulse is the main sequence of interest for deducing the ECM parameters. Taking a closer look, the profile during the pulse sequence looks as follows:

Figure 13: Closeup on HPPC pulse sequence, with a charge and discharge pulse to record the voltage response for ECM modeling purposes, current (red) and voltage (green).

The following graphs show the measured internal DC-resistances calculated from the HPPC tests, whereas the applied current pulses in charge and discharge direction were applied with a C-rate of 1C.

Figure 14: Internal resistance originating from HPPC test at 1C charge pulse.

Figure 15: Internal resistance originating from HPPC test at 1C discharge pulse.

As the results show, the internal resistance of the used cells are relatively low with a value of < 3 mΩ.

1.1.5. Results of continuous cycling at different operating conditions

Table 2: Conditions for continuous cycling tests at cell level.

10 °C	23 °C	35 °C
1 cell @ C/3 [A] charge and C/2 [A] discharge continuously	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1 cell @ C/3 [A] charge and C/2 [A] discharge continuously 1 cell @ C/3 [A] charge and 1C [A] discharge continuously 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1 cell @ C/3 [A] charge and C/2 [A] discharge continuously 1 cell @ C/3 [A] charge and 1C [A] discharge continuously

The cells were prepared for the continuous cycling test with fixtures to hold them, consisting of two rigid metal plates with the option to adjust a defined pretension force. This was to account for potential swelling and the trade-off between increasing pretension force and life expectancy of the cells. For the pretension value, the cell manufacturer had given a prerequisite in order to get a maximum in terms of their cycle life and ensure optimum conditions. For the cycling at the abovementioned temperatures, the cells were then placed inside thermal chambers, which allowed to thoroughly control the ambient temperature due to forced convection. The cells were however not actively cooled e.g. by cooling plates, which was not necessary due to the relatively moderate currents applied during the cycles. Temperature sensors were placed mainly for safety monitoring reasons directly connected to the testbench's safety system. The main focus of this experiment was to investigate the cycle life of the cells at different conditions in addition to generate checkup-test data (HPPC) along the cycles to parameterize ECM models that potentially reflect the degradation process.

Figure 16: Test setup for the continuous cycling tests. Fixtures holding the cells with a pretension force and cells being placed inside thermal chambers to set the desired ambient conditions.

During the cycle rounds, the cells were CC/CV-charged and CC-discharged continuously:

Figure 17: Continuous charge and discharge cycles; current (red), voltage (green).

The number of cycles, after which a checkup-HPPC test was done, depended mainly on the applied C-rate and the possibilities of the testbench system. For example, two cells were cycled at 35 °C, whereas after around 100 cycles a program restart was necessary and thus turned out to be a well-sized cycle round after which a rest-phase and the HPPC test was executed.

The following table shows the summary of the cycled cells, the conditions as well as the resulting SOH-decrease and the round-trip-efficiency (RTE) based on the charged and discharged energy during one cycle. All result numbers are calculated for the given cycle number.

Table 3: SOH and RTE vs. cycle number of four cells cycled at 23 °C and C/2 and 1C discharge rate.

23 °C								
	MB31, C/2		MB32, C/2		MB34, 1C		MB36, 1C	
no. of cycles	SOH/%	RTE/%	SOH/%	RTE/%	SOH/%	RTE/%	SOH/%	RTE/%
0	100.00	97.31	100.00	97.28	100.00	97.33	100.00	97.27
50	100.05	96.45	100.34	96.72	100.39	96.58	99.70	96.52
100	99.44	96.42	99.17	96.57	98.77	96.50	98.91	96.36
150	99.20	95.63	99.66	96.57	98.33	96.46	99.00	96.65
200	99.91	96.63	99.61	96.58	98.90	96.61	98.84	96.70
250	99.43	96.51	99.31	96.46	98.79	96.62	98.50	96.62
300	99.53	96.54	99.15	96.47	98.79	96.48	98.40	96.71
350	99.45	96.38	99.44	96.43	98.91	96.56	99.05	96.64

400	99.27	96.43	99.50	96.51	98.57	96.67	98.93	96.71
450				96.61	98.09	96.41		

Figure 18: SOH vs. number of cycles: moderate decrease of SOH after 400 cycles.

For the cells cycled at 23 °C, a moderate decrease of SOH after 400 cycles can be observed. A slight difference is visible between the ones with C/2 discharge rate and the 1C cycled cells. The ones at 1C show a slightly bigger decrease in SOH, as could be expected.

Table 4: SOH and RTE vs. cycle number of four cells cycled at 10 °C and C/2 and 1C discharge rate.

10 °C				
	MB33, C/2		MB35, 1C	
no. of cycles	SOH/%	RTE/%	SOH/%	RTE/%
0	100.00	95.66	100.00	95.98
50	100.86	95.67	97.34	95.22
100	100.74	95.59	97.08	95.21
150	101.18	95.97	96.66	95.25
200	100.77	95.81	96.39	95.30
250	101.06	96.12	96.20	95.26
300	101.03	96.00	95.92	95.23
350	96.96	91.12	95.75	95.23
400	96.73	91.10	95.43	95.21
450			91.10	95.19

Figure 19: SOH vs. number of cycles at 10 °C.

As expected and compared to the cells cycled at 23 °C, MB33 and MB35 show a higher decrease in SOH after 400 cycles, however, still comparatively low.

Table 5: SOH and RTE vs. cycle number of four cells cycled at 35 °C and C/2 and 1C discharge rate.

35 °C				
no. of cycles	MB136, C/2		MB106, 1C	
	SOH/%	RTE/%	SOH/%	RTE/%
0	100.00		100.00	
50	99.45	97.19	99.17	95.60
100	99.07	97.28	98.73	95.53
150	99.42	97.20	98.40	95.49
200	99.14	97.27	98.17	95.45
250	98.74	97.30	97.85	95.41
300	98.82	97.18	98.13	95.37
350	98.56	97.17	97.74	95.32
400	98.27	97.18	97.41	95.27
450	98.00	97.18	97.16	95.19
500	97.85	97.27	96.86	95.17
550	97.65	97.13	96.61	95.12
600	97.49	97.16	96.48	95.08
650	98.16	97.14	96.24	95.06
700	97.80	97.15	95.97	95.00
750			95.71	94.98
800			96.44	94.92
850			95.84	94.83
883			95.64	94.79

Figure 20: SOH vs. number of cycles at 35 °C.

In the case of the 35 °C cycles cells, the SOH decrease is at around 2.5 % after 700 cycles for the C/2 A-cycled cell and slightly higher for the 1C-cycled cell with approximately 4 % after almost 900 cycles. For these two cells, it shall be noticed that the voltage window had been reduced to 2.9 V – 4.25 V to reduce the depth of discharge and thus the potential degradation.

1.2. Module level

1.2.1. Results of the validation of the cooling design at an early development stage

For this experiment, a test setup has been created that connects two cells in parallel (1s2p) and allows for an assembly of the necessary components, that are required by the early-stage cooling concept. Those components, consisting of thermal pads, thermal fins and compression pads and the cells themselves were then pretensioned in the setup, which accounted for the same conditions as intended for the final module (where a 6s2p stack is assembled).

First, the cells were equipped with temperature sensors (thermocouples type K) to measure the temperature at their surface. Since the overall number of temperature sensors was limited (in terms of available data acquisition channels), it was decided to equip the two sides per cell differently in terms of number of sensors. The sides, which are showing to the outside (in direction of the setup fixture) were equipped with two sensors placed central at the cells' surfaces, the inner sides (the ones of both cells facing to each other) were equipped with four sensors:

Figure 21: Attachment of type-K thermocouple sensors to the cells.

According to the cooling design, both cells are sandwiched in between compression pads to account for probable cell swelling during the cells' lifetime. To conduct the heat to the top and bottom cooling plates, aluminum cooling fins are placed in between the cells and attached to cells'

surfaces by thermal pads. In terms of geometrical shape, the thermal fins are L-shaped, which allows an additional thermal coupling (with a thermal pad in between) to the top- and bottom surfaces of the cells. In between the contact areas of the thermal fins, additional sensors are placed to monitor the temperatures:

Figure 22: Placement of thermal pads and thermal fins to allow a proper thermal coupling to conduct heat to top and bottom cooling plates.

Since the setup consists of two cells, the cooling component stack in the middle is also equipped with additional sensors:

Figure 23: Adding additional temperature sensors in between the different layers (green: thermal pad, black: compression pad).

In general, the setup was assembled in a stacked way. To hold the cell-and-component sandwich, a fixture had been built with rigid metal plates and threaded bars to allow for a flexible and safe positioning as well as a pretensioning for the later investigations. From a side-view, the assembly process of the setup looks like this:

Figure 24: Side-view of the assembled cell-thermal-components-sandwich.

In addition to the mentioned components, the setup has been equipped with a force sensor type KM90 measuring up to 50 kN from ME-Messsysteme GmbH. For its attachment, the last level of the component pile shown in the previous pictures has been terminated with a floating metal plate, that acts as a contact point to the force sensor. The sensor itself was screwed to another rigid metal plate, which then was used to screw together and thus pretension the whole setup. The stack of components is located with a slight overhang at the bottom side, as the previous picture shows. This is to allow the setup, once rotated to have the cell connections on top, to be placed on a bottom cooling plate. Looking at the topside of the setup, the layers are as follows:

Figure 25: Top-side view of the test setup: Two cells are stacked with components of the thermal design and pretensioned by a screwable fixture; adding a force sensor to measure the pretension force and its evolution.

The two cooling plates, top and bottom, are attached with the same thermal pads as used in the layers between the cells. Different to the bottom plate, the top cooling side is split in two cooling rails: one for each contact side to the positive and negative cell terminals. In addition, the top cooling rails have two contact points to remove heat from the system. One is on top of the cells, where the L-shaped busbar “hugs” the cell at the topside, the other contact point is from the side, where the laser-welded-L-shaped terminal of the cell is located and provides a proper surface. The coolant inlet is then located at the bottom cooling plate, conducted to the topside where it is equally split with a y-connector to both top-cooling rails and then returned to the conditioning unit.

Taking a closer look to the topside, the different components are visible and reflect the planned overall setup as described in D7.1.

Figure 26: Closeup view of the setup - stack-layers according to test plan.

In total, 50 temperature sensors were assembled inside the whole setup. Besides the mentioned attachment in between the cells, additional sensors were placed at the sides, to monitor those areas where no cooling plate is attached; at the L-shaped parts in between the fins and the cooling

plates and finally sensors to monitor the ambient temperature as well as the welding seam temperature of one cell's L-shaped (electrical) connection tab.

Figure 27: Full overview of thermal sensors placed inside the test setup.

This conceptual cooling setup was placed at ambient temperature inside a fume hood. The test site also provided a connection to a high-current testbench, which was used to account for the planned WLTC testing and fast charging phases.

1.2.1.1. Results of basic characterization of the setup

First, the electrical characteristics of the 2p-cell compound were measured, which was done by applying standard cycles with a C/3 current rate for charge and discharge.

Figure 28: Standard Cycles @ C/3 [A] showing in upper graph: pretension force of the 2p-cell-stack (blue) and cell voltage (green); lower graph: current (red) and voltage (green).

The current shown in the above figure is the testbench current, which means that the current per cell is half of the given value (due to the 2p-cell configuration). The setup shows the voltage curve with a range of approximately 2.75 V – 4.3 V typical for NMC cells. In addition, the measured pretension force, which is shown in blue and in kg-force equivalent (the sensor value given in kilograms) is continuously recorded and shows a characteristic “breathing” behavior along the voltage curve. Starting at around 70 kgf, the force rises by around 15 kgf to 85 kgf in the first cycle. At a fully discharged cell state (in terms of minimum discharge voltage), the force is at around 25 kgf. Since the diagram shows one of the first tests with the setup, a sort of “settling” of the mechanical conditions can be observed. During the second and third standard cycle, the max. value of the force rises in addition to its amplitude. This might probably be linked to the components’ behavior of the cell stack: the flexible foam-structure of the compression pads as well as the thermal pads. In addition, the stack was assembled with the cells being at a start-SOC of close to 100 % (given the voltage at the beginning of the cycles), which then causes a mechanical adaptation of the components stacked to each other when being cycled and thus undergoing a “breathing” of the cell (which in an unconstrained setup could be observed as slight thickness changes).

In order to start off the continuous cycling by WLTC combined with fast charging phases, the pretension force was set to a value at around 120 kgf; aligned with intended mechanical conditions in the later module design. The goal was to have a defined pretension state at the beginning of the cycling to mimic the module situation, which undergoes a pretension phase during the assembly. This force was then observed over multiple WLTC cycles, whereas the intention was to not only observe potential cell degradation in terms of capacity fade of the cells, but also a potential increase of “cell-stack-pressure”. The following graph shows another standard cycle (at slightly lower C-rate) with the pretension start-value of 120 kgf.

Figure 29: Standard cycle with pretensioned cell stack showing in upper graph: pretension force of the 2p-cell-stack (blue) and cell voltage (green); lower graph: current (red) and voltage (green).

During the shown standard cycles, the force-value ranges from around 140 kgf max. to 70 kgf min., giving a delta of 70 kgf over the whole cycle.

Regarding the temperature evolution in the setup, no considerable temperature rise was observed during these standard cycles, as can be expected at the applied C-rates:

Figure 30: Temperature evolution at selected type-K sensors (left figure) and coolant temperature (right figure).

The left figure shows values of around 21 degrees at different measurement spots (placement according to abovementioned mapping figure). The two temperature increases are linked to an increase in coolant fluid temperature, which can be seen in the righthand figure. Apparently, there was a temporary control error of the conditioning unit, which was set to 20 °C of inlet temperature. Additionally, the conditioning unit showed an oscillation behavior, which was found to originate from a bent coolant pipe in the setup and thus led to a disturbance of the control loop. This issue was fixed for the further investigations.

1.2.1.2. Results of continuous CC charge/discharge cycles

As a next step, continuous charge and discharge cycles have been applied to the setup. The current was chosen to 1C for the charge direction and 2C for the discharge direction, whereas the latter was mainly to get an impression of thermal conditions during a current as high as the intended fast-charge current of 2C. Since at this stage it hadn't been clear yet, whether the cells can withstand a continuous current of 2C in the charge direction, it was first applied during discharge. Both charge and discharge phases were done only in a CC-manner, no CV-phase was applied. The voltage window for the cycles was – as previously – set to 2.75 V to 4.3 V. The cycles were applied without a rest phase in between the rounds, to ensure a continuous heat generation for validating the thermal situation in this test scenario.

The following graph shows the results of this test. In blue, the force in kgf, green is the cell voltage in V and red corresponds to the current in A, again as testbench current, meaning for both cells (2p).

Figure 31: Continuous charge/discharge cycles at 1C/2C CC-rates. Upper graph: pretension force of the 2p-cell-stack (blue) and cell voltage (green). Lower graph: current (red) and voltage (green).

The cycle round was started with another standard cycle at C/3 A, as shown in the previous section. It can be noted that the pretension force reduces its maximum value during the CC phases; whereas also the overall force-values settle between 45 kgf and 110 kgf as the number of cycles increases.

Looking at the temperatures during the cycles, expectedly, a rise in temperature is observable especially during the high-current discharge phases:

Figure 32: Temperature evolution of selected type-K sensors.

The temperatures at different spots rise after the initial standard cycle, with temporary maximums at around 38 °C and an overall mean-value at approximately 27 °C; in any case lower than 30 °C. In terms of coolant setpoints, the inlet temperature is still set to 20 °C (constant) and the flow rate is set to 2 l/min, which – considering the final cooling design for the pack – represents the maximum target flow rate per module row, of which 8 are present in the final pack and connected in parallel. The only difference between this setup's coolant flow and the final pack's one is that the coolant flows through bottom and top-cooling plates in a series connection, whereas the pack's architecture has a parallel coolant flow between top and bottom plates. Thus, calculating

the set flow rate for these experiments to the full pack, results in 4 l/min (since connected in parallel) per module cooling row and multiplied with the 8 rows per pack this sums up to 32 l/min as a maximum, full pack-related value.

1.2.1.3. Results of continuous WLTC cycling with fast charge phases

This test contains a continuous cycling of WLTC phases combined with interim fast charge phases at a current of 2C, whereas the fast charge phase is applied between 5 % SOC and 80 % SOC. As mentioned in D7.1, the benchmark vehicle, an Audi e-tron, is considered as baseline to derive the respective WLTC, whereas the current and its maximum values directly impacts the heat generation during the experiment. To deduce a current vs. time representation for the WLTC to be applied, the WLTC in its velocity vs. time representation has been considered together with drivetrain parameters and the battery pack's cell configuration, which is 96s4p in the MARBEL pack during driving (see D7.1).

Figure 33: WLTC to be applied continuously to the test setup.

The profile was applied continuously to the setup, whereas a standard cycle to get the current discharge capacity had been driven in advance. At 80 % SOC, the WLTC cycling started, whereas almost 3 full cycles could be achieved before the SOC, always referring to the capacity measured initially, was down to 5 %. As mentioned in D7.1, either a regular (C/3 A) recharge was done to 80 % or a fast charge at 2C, depending on a calculated value for the distance driven during the WLTC cycling. This distance was calculated based on the simple assumption, that one full WLTC corresponds to 22 km.

Figure 34: Excerpt from the continuous WLTC cycling with interim fast charge phase at slightly reduced C-rate. Upper graph: pretension force of the 2p-cell-stack (blue) and cell voltage (green). Lower graph: current (red) and voltage (green).

The figure shows a snapshot in the middle of the continuous cycling. The WLTC cycles, three in a row, can be seen before the SOC reaches 5% and thus a recharge at C/3 is initiated. In addition, the chosen excerpt in the figure shows a fast charge phase at approximately 1.4C charge current, which is because the current has been ramped up steadily with each cycle round to get close to the 2C and detect potential problems at this high C-rate at an early stage. The lowest current in the first round was set to 1.12C. Looking at the seventh cycle round, the current was at its intended level of 2C:

Figure 35: Excerpt from the continuous WLTC cycling with interim fast charge phase at target current of 2C. Upper graph: pretension force of the 2p-cell-stack (blue) and cell voltage (green). Lower graph: current (red) and voltage (green).

Considering the intended test procedure, the WLTC cycles should have been continued until an estimated number of 2000 km was reached, before a fast charge phase is initiated. The whole cycle round then should end after 6000 km with two fast charges. However, the test sequence assumed that 4 consecutive WLTC could be driven before the cells need to be recharged. As can be seen in the previous figures, only 3 WLTC were possible before reaching the low SOC value. This is linked to a reduced voltage window of 2.9 V – 4.2 V, that was used during the cycles as a limiting criterion but also during the standard cycle, which had been applied at the start of each cycling round. Thus, the initial measured capacity, that was used to limit the SOC during the WLTC phase was slightly lower, which led to an earlier abortion of the WLTC cycles. As a result, the fast charge phases were initiated before reaching 2000 km, resulting in a total distance of estimated, driven kilometers per cycle round of 4000 km. It was decided to keep this sequence, since it accounts for a “worse case” scenario than the one with 6000 km per round, since in the end the total number of fast charges is increased. Therefore, for the sake of investigating the degradation behavior under these conditions as well as detecting potential thermal problems with such demanding cycles, the cycle rounds were continued until an estimated total distance of 43500 km was reached with the test setup.

Figure 36: Temperature evolution of selected type-K sensors during the WLTC cycles and 2C fast charge.

The temperatures during the experiment peak at around 38 °C max. value, expectedly during the 2C fast charge. The figure also shows a very slight increase in temperature during the WLTC phases, whereas the overall temperature is in a range of 23 °C – 27 °C, depending on the sensor position in the test setup. For example, sensor “T9” shows the lowest temperature with 23 °C, which is because the sensor position is at the top of the first cell, positive terminal side, where the L-shaped aluminum fin has direct contact to the top cooling rail that conducts the 20 °C conditioned coolant at 2 l/min. In contrast to that, sensor “T45” shows the highest value, which is because it sits at the side surface and upper half of cell 1, with no contact to any cooling-channel or -component. When comparing sensors “T6” and “T30”, the latter is always slightly higher than “T6”, which is because it sits on the outside of cell 2 toward the pressure plate, where no cooling fin is conducting heat towards the coolant plates. “T6” in contrast sits at cell 1 in between the cell’s surface and the thermal pad, which – during less demanding phases – leads to a slightly lower

temperature than “T31” due to the fins heat dissipation. It can be summarized that the temperatures are neither critical during the fast charge phases, nor during the WLTC phases.

Additionally, the change of pretension force as well as the decrease of capacity has been monitored during the continuous WLTC cycling. The following table shows the result values along the repeated cycling sequences.

Table 6: Resulting values from the continuous WLTC cycling with fast charge phases.

round	estimated km	SOH / %	kgf start	kgf end	delta kgf	C-rate fCHA
1	3960	100	98.7	147.7	49.0	1.12
2	7920	99.53	113.0	149.0	36.0	1.12
3	11880	99.42	142.2	149.6	7.5	1.21
4	15840	99.31	150.0	149.6	-0.3	1.38
5	19800	99.31	148.3	150.3	1.9	1.64
6	23760	99.28	148.3	151.3	2.9	1.81
7	27720	99.14	125.3	151.3	26.0	2.00
8	31680	99.50	151.9	150.3	-1.6	2.00
9	35640	99.58	145.0	154.0	9.0	2.00
10	39600	99.39	154.0	156.0	2.0	2.00
11	43560	99.14	153.0	155.0	2.0	2.00

The SOH was calculated based on the discharge capacity that had been measured at the beginning of each cycle and based on the very first cycle’s discharge capacity. It shows a low decrease during the cycling rounds of < 1 %.

Figure 37: SOH based on discharge capacity and relative to initial capacity during WLTC cycles with fast charge phases.

Figure 38: Evolution of pretension force of the cell stack setup vs. cycle rounds.

When evaluating the pretension force and its change over the number of cycles, it can be observed that the delta between the start and end values per cycle round decreases with an increasing number of cycles. Some outliers, e.g. the one at the seventh round can be explained by a manual readjustment of pretension force in the setup due to a mechanical rearrangement during the experimental phase. Therefore, the value starts at a slightly lower force value at the cycle round's start and led to an increase in delta.

As a results of this experiment, it can be concluded that this conceptual setup was capable of providing a module-like structure in terms of cooling components as well as a compound of cells to be tested. The results show that the cooling concept as implemented in the setup is capable of maintaining a safe temperature window during demanding cycles as well as fast charging phases. In addition, the setpoint of coolant was kept constant for all cycle rounds, at a temperature of 20 °C. Obviously, the cooling system could set lower inlet temperatures in case of e.g. higher ambient temperatures or more demanding driving cycles. The results of this setup have also contributed to a conference article about a virtual development of a thermal management system [1].

Regarding the degradation that was caused by these cycles, no significant loose of capacity-related SOH is found. The overall pretension force shows a slight increase as the cycles are applied, whereas the difference between the start and end of cycle is comparably low. During the cycles, a breathing of the cells is observable. It shall be noted again that the full intended fast charge current of 2C had not been applied from the beginning, but was ramped up to iteratively check the cell's behavior. In addition, the voltage window was reduced during the cycles, which means the depth of discharge (DOD) was also lower. Both might have a considerable influence on the observed degradation behavior.

1.2.2. Results of the electrical and thermal validation of a full module

This test was intended to validate the functionality and the characteristics of a full MARBEL module, by communicating with the BMS-CAN-channel and by applying different test profiles, as the ones described above at cell level. Since at this stage of test, no full pack had been available so far, the test setup was extended to account for the cooling of the module, whereas the setup's design was fully aligned with the cooling system design of the full pack.

Thus, two cooling plates were manufactured that were tailored to the module's size. Since the full pack's housing integrates the bottom cooling plate by conducting the coolant through the base plate the modules are screwed to, the module in this experiment was placed onto a small cooling plate with the same cooling channel layout as the pack's base plate. For the top cooling rail, a U-shaped profile was used to conduct the heat from the terminals, which provide a flat plateau surface for attaching the module's top cover plate and the latter to the top cooling rail:

Figure 39: Bottom cooling plate with type K sensors to place the module on.

For the measurement of the heat transfer at selected spots of the module, type K thermal sensors were placed at the bottom plate. The module, which comes with assembled L-shape terminals on its bottom side and attached thermal pad, could therefore directly be placed on the cooling plate. Since the plate was manufactured from the same profiles as used for the full pack and due to its reduced length, both ends had to be welded to tighten the coolant flow.

Figure 40: Module placed on bottom cooling plate.

In the same way, type K sensors were placed on top of the module. The assembled top cover plate, which thermally connects the welded cell tabs with their flat surface to the top cooling rail, came with assembled thermal pads as well. Therefore, the sensors could directly be placed in the thermal pad layer before placing the top cooling rail.

Figure 41: Top cooling rail placed on module's top cover plate.

In addition to the sensors placed in the heat conducting path between module and coolant plates, sensors were placed at the busbars, to monitor the thermal conditions during applied cycles.

Especially the series connection between two parallel cells was of interest, since the full current of two cells ($2p$) flows through this connection. For the same reason, a sensor was placed close to the welding seam of the welded cell tabs and at the module's main connection where it is connection to the testbench. The latter was especially to investigate a potential impact of the attached testbench cables, which might contribute to a heat dissipation from the terminals due to the cable's thermal mass (cross-section 70 mm^2).

Figure 42: Additional type K sensor measurement spots due to potential thermal influences.

The following figure shows the final placement of measurement sensors in the setup.

Figure 43: Placement of type K sensors for the module setup with attached cooling plates.

Considering the assembly situation in the full pack, the modules are screwed to the base plate / bottom cooling plate of the pack with their fixation eyelets. For the top cooling rail, the top cover plate of the pack accounts for a proper pressure force to ensure a good thermal contact. Thus, a simple fixture clamping the top and bottom plate together to “sandwich” the module was assembled for this specific setup. This fixture allowed to thoroughly adjust the pressing force of the plates in relation to the module.

To test the communication via CAN as well as the electrical behavior of the module, multiple standard cycles have been applied. In this specific case, the charge current has been set to $C/6$

to allow a moderate charge and a potential balancing if necessary; the discharge current has been set to $C/2$.

Figure 44: Standard cycles at moderate C-rates to check electrical behavior and CAN communication, current (red), voltage (green).

During the test, the CAN-communication has been logged and communicated to the testbench via CAN, in order to react to potential error/warning messages and to cut the current flow in case of exceeding the safe operating area (e.g. max. voltage). Therefore, the cell voltages have been logged in addition to errors/warnings.

Figure 45: Cell voltages received via CAN-communication during the standard cycle.

The cell voltages seem well balanced, with a slight deviation of cell voltage 2. Depending on the charge current, the balancing gets activated by the BMS to even out such voltage deltas. As can be seen in the figures above, the cell voltages as well as the module voltage were limited at a higher value than expectable at a fully discharged system. For the cells, the limitation was set at around 3.65 V, which summed up to a module voltage of 21.9 V. The reason for this limitation was due to an unexpected behavior of the module's BMS, which caused the communicated cell voltages to freeze whenever the voltage was lower than the mentioned 3.65 V:

Figure 46: Freeze of CAN communication during standard cycle, module current (red), module voltage (green).

Figure 47: Freeze of CAN-cell voltage values during standard cycle.

According to the results, the values freeze during the discharge phase. It was found that the freeze of the cell voltages was linked to a loss of CAN-communication and thus the testbench record was fixed to the last received value. The loss of communication was further caused by a complete shutdown of the BMS slave board, which is connected to the iSCMs to collect the single 2p-cell-compound values (mainly voltage and temperature). Normally, this loss of CAN communication would have let to an abortion of the experiment, however, after repeating this experiment to understand the cause, it was found that the shutdown of BMS board reproducibly happened at cell voltages lower than approximately 3.65 V. Therefore, the test system's abortion mechanism due to a timeout in CAN-communication was deactivated for a further repetition of the test, whereas the full cycle was monitored with additional cell voltage measurement provided by the testbench. To investigate a potential recovery of the module slave board, the module has been charged again to higher values, which revealed a switch-on of the module slave board when the module voltage was higher than approximately 23 V. With this activation, also the CAN-communication was reactivated and values were received again.

To validate what the exact criterion for this shutdown was, either the cell voltages being as low as 3.65 V or the module voltage being lower than 21.9 V, an experimental setup has been created with only the BMS slave and iSCM board connected together and laboratory power supplies acting as the single cells. This setup allowed a fast and reproducible experimentation, without the need to charge/discharge the module and cells to understand the behavior.

Figure 48: Experimental setup with BMS components and power-supply "cells" to dynamically investigate the shutdown issue.

By changing the different "cell" voltages with the lab power supplies, it was found that not the single cell voltage caused the issue, as can be seen in the above figure. In this case, the second cell voltage was tuned down to 3.33 V (which caused the other "cells" to start balancing as can be seen by the currents of approximately 200 mA), while still maintaining the correct functioning of the BMS slave board (indicated by the green LED in the picture, left), which is also shown by the correct 12 V supplied LIN-communication, which connects the iSCMs with the slave board. Thus, in further experiments, multiple "cells" were tuned down to lower voltages and it turned out that the criterion for the shutdown was linked to the overall module voltage. Therefore, whenever a value lower than 21.9 V was reached, the slave board did shut off and stop the communication.

Unfortunately, to the time of writing this deliverable, the root cause and with it a potential solution to the problem has not been found yet, which was also due to limited time during the last stages of the experimental phase. This impacted the ability to perform a full cycle with the module, at least in terms of validating the full communication and functionality of the BMS. Obviously, with respect to electrical performance, the full cycle was driven and didn't pose any problems, however, temporarily no CAN-communication was received by the BMS. The cause and possible solutions are still being investigated for future experiments and an overall improvement of the performance. As a matter of fact, the communications do work as expected when the abovementioned voltage limits are not exceeded, which indicates that the shutdown issue might be linked to e.g. the power supply of the slave board which is drawn from the module's voltage connection.

1.2.3. Results of the interconnection of modules to build “pack-like” structure

Considering the slave-board issue described in the previous section, it was foreseen that the fully cycle could neither be performed with interconnected modules. However, the interconnection allowed for a validation of the daisy-chaining and functioning of the BMS in a group-configuration, as it is present in the full battery pack. Additionally, the experiments allowed at least for the limited voltage window a comparison between the cooled module attached to the cooling plates and two uncooled modules, which were then connected in series.

Figure 49: Interconnection of 3 modules in series to create a “mini-pack”.

Figure 50: Modules interconnected in 3s configuration during a standard cycle. Uppermost figure: module voltage (green) and current (red), lower three figures: cell voltages 1-18.

As the results show, the interconnection and communication via CAN works well. The values of all three modules are received by the testbench, which allows for a monitoring to stay within the safe operating area. From the lowermost figure above, it can be noticed that module 3 (cells 13-18) shows a slightly better balance of cell voltages, which is because it has been balanced manually before starting the experiment. However, whenever the modules are charged and the current is low enough to allow for a proper balancing (current of approximately 200 mA per 2p-cell-compound), the BMS activates it, and the cell voltages are evened out.

Even though the full cycle couldn't be applied and thus neither a demanding cycle was applied due to safety reasons, the difference in temperature between the cooled module 2 and the uncooled modules 1 and 3 could be observed:

Figure 51: Modules interconnected in 3s configuration during a standard cycle. Uppermost figure: module voltage (green) and current (red), lower three figures: cell temperatures 1-18.

Especially during the discharge phase at C/2 it is observable that the modules 1 and 3, the ones without active cooling, reach temperatures of approximately 3-4 °C higher than module 2, which is the one attached between the cooling plates. The setpoints of coolant during this experiment were fixed to 20 °C inlet temperature and a flow rate of 1.7 l/min, still below the maximum flow rate of 2 l/min per module row. Compared to the previously described concept cooling test setup, the connection of the upper and lower cooling plate this time is parallel; whereas it was series connected for the former. Therefore, both cooling rails are fed with the same inlet temperature. Therefore, even though no demanding cycle could be applied to the module so far, it can be assumed that the cooling system in the final module design influences the temperatures noticeably, whereas a full evaluation of its performance cannot be given yet due to the limited data available.

1.3. Pack level

1.3.1. Results of the vibration test

For the vibration test according to the UNECE R100 standard, the pack was mounted on a vibration table to apply the respective vibration profile. The 400 V pack provides 4 fixation eyelets

at its sides, that are welded to the housing frame over their entire perimeter. Close to the fixation eyes, control accelerometers have been placed to control the applied testing profile.

Figure 52: Test setup for vibration test: 400 V pack is securely fixed to vibration table.

In addition, an accelerometer is placed in the centre and on top of the battery pack, to monitor and record the acceleration during the test in x, y and z-axis.

During and before the vibration test, there were several problems, that finally led to an abortion of the test. First, the main contactors could not be closed due to an isolation error that was reported by the isolation monitoring unit of the pack. During the assembly phase, it has been found that using the same power supply for BMS electronics at the low-voltage connector of the pack and the isolation board leads to a potential drift that is reported as an error by the isolation board. Thus, it was suggested to use separate power supplies for both electronic units. Even though two separate and isolated power supplies (vehicle board net 12 V batteries) were used to power the BMS electronics separately from the isolation board, the latter still measured an electric potential fault and thus prevented the contactors from being closed. This negated the execution of a standard cycle before and also after the vibration test.

During the vibration test, not only the accelerations were monitored but also the BMS-CAN-traffic, which was possible even though the contactors had not been closed. The main focus was on monitoring potential errors/warnings during the test, but also link the measured voltages per module as safety criteria to the testbench system.

After approximately 20 minutes of vibration test time, the BMS communicated module voltages did show an unexpected behavior and thus led to the abortion of the vibration test.

Figure 53: Vibration test of 400 V pack, first half cycle, from top to bottom: FFT x, y and z-axis.

Figure 54: Vibration test of 400 V pack, second half cycle, from top to bottom: FFT x, y and z-axis.

After almost the full first out of 12 cycles had been complete (after approximately 12 minutes), the module voltage of module 2 dropped to zero and showed an oscillating behavior. While other modules also showed a step in the voltage value at that time, the dropping to zero caused the vibration test to abort:

Figure 55: Module voltages of modules 1-4 during the vibration test: module 2 causes an abortion of the test.

Considering the the behavior of the module voltages, the issue could be linked to a communication-based problem. Based on the previous experiences at module level that led to a freeze in values due to a communication loss, this issue could originate from a software-based point of view. However, it is more probable that a mechanical issue could be the cause. Since the iSCM boards that communicate values to the slave boards of the modules are connected with plugs via LIN, the vibrations could lead to bad contact conditions. On the other hand, the voltage measurement connection per cell and per module – whereas the latter is used to power the BMS slave boards – could be impacted by the vibration test and thus lead to a drift/jumping in potential.

After the vibration test, the top cover lid has been opened to take a look inside the pack. Doing that, some loose screws were found that apparently were used to fix the modules top cover plates and the top cooling rails at the front end of the rows:

Figure 56: Opened 400 V pack after vibration test abortion: some loose screws were found at the marked spots.

Although the vibration test had not been performed for the full 3 hour duration, it can be regarded as success. It revealed potential weak-points of the communications, which considering the module-linked difficulties is a good lever point for future improvement. In addition, it showed that some fixation concepts / tools need to be adapted to account for vibrations and thus a potential loosening of parts. It shall be mentioned however, that the isolation problem that initially prevented the contactors from being closed had been present even before the vibration was started. Thus, it is not very likely that the isolation problem was linked to loose parts; whereas in contrast the pack had not been checked for loose parts before the vibration test. Therefore, it could also be linked to the previous transport of the pack. No matter what exactly led to loose screws, this is a valuable feedback and result from the test, which had been the main purpose in the first place.

1.3.2. Coolant distributor test

1.3.2.1. Scope of test

To have temperature homogeneity in the battery pack the coolant distributor, see Figure 57, must ensure that each parallel row of the cooling channels have nearly identical volume flow.

Figure 57: Top and bottom cooling rails with distributor.

The volume flow homogeneity is realised with predefined throttles integrated into the inlet side of the coolant distributor for the bottom and top cooling rails. The diameters of those throttles are determined by 3D-CFD simulations considering the complete flow path from inlet to outlet. The volume flow optimization is described in D3.5 of MARBEL project.

1.3.2.2. Test setup

To test and validate the design a simple experimental setup was built. Figure 58 indicates the schematic structure of the test for the bottom flow distributor. Since only 1 flow sensor was available the complete flow path from inlet to outlet cannot be tested. The current setup only considers the inlet flow side including the throttles.

Figure 58: Coolant distributor test setup.

The test procedure consists of the following steps:

1. Adjust the flow rate to 16 litres per minute and let the water flow for exactly 3 minutes (containers must be empty before the start).
2. Stop the volume flow.
3. Measure the liquid volume in the containers 1-8.
4. Repeat the test several times.

1.3.2.3. Test results

Considering the complete flow path from inlet to outlet the pressure loss inside the intake is about 50% of the complete pressure drop. The resulting flow distribution in the current test setup due to the missing pressure loss of downstream flow cannot be even. The pressure level at the container inlets is atmospheric for each of the 8 rows, which is different from the pressure level what is present in case of complete flow path. Therefore, the experimental results can only be compared with a 3D-CFD simulation result of the same layout. This leads to a validated 3D-CFD setup with which the flow distribution in complete system can be determined and trusted.

The above-described experimental setup was built by AVL-IT, see Figure 59.

Figure 59: Experimental setup of coolant distributor test.

In the followings the results after 10 repeated steps are shown, for the top rail in Table 7, and for the bottom rail in Table 8.

Table 7: Flow rates of top inlet side.

TOP INLET											
Test	Flow rate (l/min)	Fill time (s)	Nozzle 1 (l/min)	Nozzle 2 (l/min)	Nozzle 3 (l/min)	Nozzle 4 (l/min)	Nozzle 5 (l/min)	Nozzle 6 (l/min)	Nozzle 7 (l/min)	Nozzle 8 (l/min)	Totale (l)
1	16	180	3.3	2.0	1.4	1.3	1.4	0.2	2.1	3.5	15.2
2	16	180	3.5	2.1	1.3	1.3	1.4	0.2	2.1	3.6	15.4
3	16	180	3.2	1.9	1.3	1.2	1.2	1.2	2.0	3.3	15.3
4	16	180	3.4	2.2	0.5	1.3	1.3	0.5	2.2	3.6	14.9
5	16	180	2.8	2.0	1.4	1.2	1.2	1.2	2.0	3.3	15.2
6	16	180	3.4	2.2	0.2	1.3	1.2	1.3	2.1	3.4	15.2
7	16	180	2.9	1.9	1.3	1.1	1.2	1.2	2.1	3.1	14.8
8	16	180	3.5	2.2	0.5	1.2	1.2	1.0	2.2	3.4	15.2
9	16	180	3.1	2.1	1.3	1.2	1.4	0.3	2.3	3.6	15.2
10	16	180	3.3	2.2	0.5	1.3	1.2	1.3	2.1	3.2	15.1
Mean	16	180	3.2	2.1	1.0	1.2	1.3	0.8	2.1	3.4	15.1
Sim			3.0	2.0	1.3	1.4	1.4	1.4	2.0	3.0	15.5

Table 8: Flow rates of bottom inlet side.

BOTTOM INLET											
Test	Flow rate (l/min)	Fill time (s)	Nozzle 1 (l/min)	Nozzle 2 (l/min)	Nozzle 3 (l/min)	Nozzle 4 (l/min)	Nozzle 5 (l/min)	Nozzle 6 (l/min)	Nozzle 7 (l/min)	Nozzle 8 (l/min)	Total (l)
1	16	180	4.5	0.8	1.1	1.0	1.0	0.8	0.8	4.0	13.9
2	16	180	4.4	2.4	0.7	1.0	1.1	1.0	0.7	4.8	16.0
3	16	180	4.7	2.4	0.7	1.0	1.1	1.0	0.9	4.8	16.6
4	16	180	4.3	0.6	1.1	0.9	0.9	0.8	0.6	3.8	12.9
5	16	180	4.7	2.4	0.7	0.9	1.0	1.0	0.7	4.8	16.2
6	16	180	4.7	2.4	0.7	1.0	1.0	1.0	0.7	5.0	16.6
7	16	180	5.1	2.9	1.2	1.0	1.2	0.3	3.1	5.4	20.1
8	16	180	4.5	0.5	1.6	0.8	0.9	0.9	0.6	4.1	13.9
9	16	180	5.3	2.7	0.7	1.1	1.0	0.3	2.9	4.6	18.6
10	16	180	4.5	0.6	0.9	0.9	0.9	0.8	0.8	3.9	13.3
Mean	16	180	4.6	1.8	0.9	1.0	1.0	0.8	1.2	4.5	15.8
Sim			3.8	1.6	0.8	0.8	0.9	1.0	1.6	3.6	14.0

Figure 60: Comparison of results exp. vs. simulation for top rail.

Figure 61: Comparison of results exp. vs. simulation for bottom rail.

In Figure 60 and Figure 61 the comparison of the mean fill rates with simulation results are shown. The presented results show an acceptable but not perfect agreement between the 3D-CFD simulation and the experiment, indicating in an indirect manner that a small amount of flow inhomogeneity is present in the complete system.

1.3.3. Results of Cybersecurity Tests

1.3.3.1. Introduction

The cybersecurity testing activities were initially planned to be conducted at the pack level, as outlined in D7.1. However, due to the unavailability of the complete pack, the scope of testing was adapted to focus on the available modules. Even at module level, the testing options were limited, as the modules and iSCM software versions supplied did not correspond to the final and definitive version.

As a result, testing efforts were concentrated primarily on the Bluetooth functionalities of the iSCMs. It is important to note that achieving a high level of security for the iSCM was never within the scope of the MARBEL project. According to the MARBEL grant agreement, cybersecurity objectives commenced at the gateway level, focusing on securing communication between the gateway and the cloud to enable secure data transfer. Therefore, no definitive assessment regarding the overall security level of the iSCMs can be made, nor was such an evaluation intended within the scope of these tests.

Nonetheless, based on the findings from the tests performed, recommendations are provided to support future projects in further strengthening cybersecurity awareness and practices.

1.3.3.2. Test setup

Figure 62: Test setup of cybersecurity tests.

The setup used during the testing activities is illustrated in Figure 62. The MARBEL module, serving as the Device Under Test (DUT), was connected to a CAN logger to capture and monitor CAN bus traffic throughout the assessment. An external antenna was attached to a development laptop to enable external stimulation of the module's iSCMs. For this purpose, a custom script was developed utilizing the *Bleak* library, a Bluetooth Low Energy (BLE) client capable of interacting with devices acting as GATT servers. The script established a connection to the target Bluetooth device and transmitted a series of commands and messages, designed to stimulate various functionalities as described in the following section.

1.3.3.3. Test execution

Penetration testing in the cybersecurity domain often involves exploratory activities, where various techniques are applied to observe system behavior under abnormal conditions. The following tests were performed during the assessment:

- **Denial of Service (DoS):**
Attempts were made to disrupt the operation of the iSCMs by transmitting a high volume of messages in a short period, aiming to overload and potentially shut down the devices.

- **Message Spoofing:**

Several spoofing techniques were tested to evaluate the robustness of the iSCMs against unauthorized or malformed input:

- Modifying the internal name of the iSCM.
- Attempting to overflow the internal memory allocated for the iSCM name to trigger unexpected behavior.
- Sending shutdown or sleep commands to the iSCMs to induce sleep mode, potentially interrupting data transfer and placing the module in a hazardous state.

The original plan was to perform a man-in-the-middle (MitM) attack by spoofing messages to the slave BMS, which impersonated iSCM by using the *FlipperZero* security device. However, this attack scenario could not be carried out because the present version of the slave BMS software worked via the LIN protocol at that time, which meant that Bluetooth-based spoofing attempts in this direction of communication were not feasible. Nevertheless, this vector is considered a significant potential attack surface for future assessments.

1.3.3.4. Test results

The results of the tests carried out can be summarized as follows:

- **Denial of Service (DoS):**

The DoS attempts did not succeed in shutting down the iSCMs. The devices appeared to implement a basic rate-limiting mechanism, accepting only a limited number of messages (approximately 16) per second, thereby mitigating the effectiveness of the flooding attempts.

- **Message Spoofing:**

- Modifying the internal name of the iSCM was successfully achieved.
- Attempts to overflow the internal memory allocated for the device name were unsuccessful.
- Sending sleep mode commands to the iSCMs was successful, and the devices could be placed into sleep mode, potentially interrupting normal data transfer operations.

1.3.3.5. Discussion

As outlined previously, the test results do not permit a definitive conclusion regarding the overall security posture of the iSCMs. Nonetheless, to enhance security levels in future projects and developments, the following recommendations are provided:

- **Authentication of Communication Partners:**

To mitigate the risk of message spoofing, communication partners should be authenticated not only by MAC address but also through a secure authentication mechanism. Suitable methods could include a lightweight challenge-response scheme (e.g., based on HMAC), the use of pre-shared keys with message signing, or Bluetooth LE Secure Connections with bonding. Given the resource constraints on the iSCMs, any solution must remain lightweight.

Implementing authentication would ensure that only authorized communication partners can transmit commands, preventing unauthorized modifications such as internal name changes or forced sleep mode activation. In particular, commands that alter configuration settings should only be accepted by senders who have been granted elevated privileges.

- **Protection Against Man-in-the-Middle (MitM) Attacks:**

The risk of MitM attacks can be reduced by applying secure digital signatures or message

authentication codes to the data transmitted to the Slave-BMS. This measure would help verify the integrity and authenticity of communications, ensuring that only legitimate and unaltered data is accepted.

- Confidentiality of Bluetooth Data:**
 It should be evaluated whether the data transmitted over the Bluetooth channel is sensitive or subject to confidentiality requirements. If confidentiality is a concern, appropriate encryption mechanisms should be implemented to protect the data during transmission.

2. Test procedures related to safety validation

2.1. Cell level

2.1.1. Results of Thermal Abuse Test

The thermal abuse test for the cell has been carried out following specific test conditions: The cell is heated at a rate of 4 °C/min from 10 °C to 155 °C. At this temperature the thermal runaway is triggered as shown in the figures below.

Figure 63: Temperature distribution of the cell during the thermal abuse test.

Figure 64: Temperature distribution of the cell during the thermal abuse test.

From the temperature distribution plot given in Figure 64 represents the cell reached the maximum temperature around 900 °C and the temperature is gradually rising from the beginning of the test, when the thermal runaway is triggered, it reached the maximum temperature of **907.7 °C** in the 36th minute of the test from the centre of the cell.

Figure 65: Temperature distribution on the cell when the thermal runaway is triggered.

The above figure shows the exact moment when thermal runaway occurs, at about $t = 2210$ s.

Figure 66: The voltage plot over time during thermal abuse test.

Figure 66 shows a sudden drop in voltage when thermal runaway is initiated and the cell is destroyed, losing all functionality. With this test, the maximum temperature that the cell can withstand has been demonstrated to be between 150 °C - 160 °C.

Figure 67: Front and top view of the cell for thermal abuse test setup.

Figure 68: Initial stages of thermal runaway during thermal abuse test.

Figure 69: Final moments of Thermal runaway during thermal abuse test.

Figure 70: The cell condition after thermal runaway in the thermal abuse test.

A further relevant aspect to validate with this test was the functionality of the venting valve of the cell. As illustrated in the Figure 70, a fracture was observed in lateral of the cell housing, indicating a malfunction of the valve.

2.1.2. Results of Overcharge Test

In the overcharge test, the cell was already charged to 100 % state of charge, and the charging current was applied to the cell exceeding the maximum operational voltage to trigger the thermal runaway. In this test the cell reaches the maximum temperature of 660 °C.

Figure 71: Front view and top view of the cell overcharge test setup.

The voltage of the cell during the overcharge test reached a maximum voltage of 9.65 V when the thermal runaway is triggered and then drops down to 0 V as soon as the thermal runaway is started as given in the Figure 734.

Figure 72: Temperature distribution over the cell during overcharge test.

Figure 73: Temperature distribution when the thermal runaway is triggered during overcharge test.

Figure 74: The voltage plot for the overcharge test.

Figure 75: The cell condition after overcharge test.

Figure 76: Thermal images of the overcharge test.

The infrared thermal camera is used to see the temperature distribution of the cell, and for a better understanding of the temperature distribution through the entire thermal runaway process.

2.1.3. Results of Drop Test

The drop test cell has been tied to the test setup to drop the cell from 1 m as per the testing standards (UN 38.3). To study the adverse results and the behaviour of the cell, the cell is dropped so that it hits the flat surface, which is the weakest surface for structural deformations of the cell.

Figure 77: Drop test setup for the cell.

With the drop test, no venting, fire or explosion has been observed from the cell after the resting period as well. The effect of drop test which was experienced was a slight deformation on the structure of the cell. The voltage of the cell had no major difference before and after the test.

2.1.4. Results of Impact Test

Figure 78: The Impact Test Setup for the Cell.

The DUTs had been tested to validate the withstanding capabilities for the mechanical impact on the system for the real-world scenarios (UN38.3). The test cell results from impact of the stainless-steel bar have been detailed below. With the impact test, no venting, fire or explosion has been observed from the cell after the resting period as well. The effect of impact test which experienced no deformation on the structure of the cell except the mark of impact area. The voltage of the cell had no major difference before and after the test.

Figure 79: The test cell and the impact test setup.

Figure 80: The impact on the cell surface after the test.

2.1.5. Results of Nail Penetration Test

The nail penetration test is the major test for safety standards due to its violent and intrusive nature, triggering an internal short circuit during the process. In order to validate the safety by intentionally triggering the thermal runaway, the cell behaviour in adverse conditions as real driving conditions when the cell is exposed to crash, accident scenarios. The test results are shown below.

Figure 81: The nail penetration test setup for the cell.

Figure 82: The temperature distribution on the major surfaces of the cell once the thermal runaway is initiated.

The cell reached a maximum of 739 °C on the surface where the nail penetrated the cell.

Figure 83: The temperature plot focusing on temperature rise when thermal runaway is triggered.

Figure 84: The voltage plot over time during nail penetration test.

The test cell images after the nail penetration are given in the figure below.

Figure 85: The nail penetration test setup and the test cell after thermal runaway.

Figure 86: When the thermal runaway is initiated in the cell using thermal camera.

Figure 87: When the thermal runaway is initiated in normal image.

2.1.6. Results of Crush Test

The crush test simulates mechanical abuse by applying a compressive force to the test cell, evaluating its behaviour under mechanical stress conditions. The goal is to observe structural deformations and possible internal reactions caused by external forces on the cell surface. The test is done on the widest surface of the cell, and the results indicate physical deformation on the sides of the cell structure. No gas venting, fire, or explosion occurred during the test or the subsequent rest period. Additionally, the results show no significant temperature variation once deformation begins.

Figure 88: The crush test setup for the test cell.

Figure 89: Temperature variation on the cell during mechanical loading.

The test cell experienced temperature variation only on the cell surface where the mechanical load is applied and the other surface of the cell had minimum temperature variation during the mechanical loading. Moreover, the temperature deviation experienced on the surface might be

due to the compression force on thermal sensor because the temperature on the other surfaces of the cell has minimal deviation.

Figure 90: The temperature effect during the mechanical loading on the weakest side of the cell.

The cell voltage of the test cell had very minimum deviation effect with the mechanical loading on the cell surface. The voltage is being constant between 3.73 V and 3.75 V during the whole duration of the crush test.

Figure 91: The cell voltage during the test duration.

The results of test cell are given in the figure below.

Figure 92: The crush test setup and the test cell after mechanical loading with deformation.

2.2. Module level

2.2.1. Results of Thermal Abuse Test

Figure 93: The thermal abuse test for the module.

The thermal abuse test has a lesser effect on the module. The maximum recorded temperature was 145.7 °C, indicating that the module exhibited adequate thermal stability. It is notable that no instances of thermal runaway were observed following the completion of the test, as the temperature did not exceed the threshold of 150 – 160 °C, which is the temperature range that has been documented to initiate thermal runaway events in cell-level testing.

Figure 94: Temperature distribution plot for the module during thermal abuse test.

Figure 95: The thermal image of thermal abuse test for the module.

The voltage had minimum deviation during the test when compared the values before and after the test from the measurements.

Figure 96: The voltage drops in the module during thermal abuse test.

2.2.2. Results of Drop Test

Figure 97: The drop test setup for the module.

With the drop test, no venting, fire or explosion has been observed from the module after the resting period as well. The effect of drop test which was experienced was a slight deformation on the top lid structure of the module. The voltage of the module had no major difference before and after the test.

2.2.3. Results of Impact Test

The DUTs had been tested to validate the withstanding capabilities for the mechanical impact on the system for the real-world scenarios. The test cell results from impact of the stainless-steel bar have been detailed below.

Figure 98: The impact setup for the module and the initial measurements before the impact test.

The impact test on the module demonstrated that the module was able to withstand the test without failure, thus demonstrating the module's resilience and the quality of the developed

module. The outcomes of the aforementioned tests have showed that the module has passed the test.

2.2.4. Results of Crush Test

Figure 99: The crush test setup for the module.

The results show no evidence of exothermic reaction when the crushing force is applied to the module.

Figure 100: The temperature distribution over time on the module during the crush test.

From the figures, we conclude that the temperature on the other surfaces of the module other than the load was applied remained low and constant which shows the temperature deviation on the surface where the load is applied may be a noise of the temperature sensor because of compression load which made a contact with the sensor and so it can be neglected. The results show the crush test has no impact from the test and the device has passed the crush test due to its withstand capabilities.

Figure 101: The Temperature distribution on the remaining surface in the module except the mechanical loaded surface.

The voltage of the module remained constant during the entire crush test as shown in Figure 102.

Figure 102: The voltage plot for module during crush test.

2.3. Pack Level (400 V System)

Due to time constraints, only one of the planned tests for safety validation at pack level could be carried out after the vibration test on the 400 V pack. This additional test was also subcontracted to the company carrying out the vibration test, since due to a delayed availability of the full packs and a reduction of assembled 400 V packs to 1 instead of 2, a full testing campaign as planned in D7.1 could not be achieved, also considering the necessary transportation between the vibration test facility and the abusive test facility, which would have further delayed the testing process.

In this test, a thermal runaway of a cell was provoked in order to be able to assess the potential thermal propagation in the pack. The thermal runaway of a cell was achieved by overheating with four heat pads placed around the cell.

2.3.1. Preparation and Test Setup

The heat pads were placed around a cell in the middle of module 8. The positions of the heat pads and of the type K thermal sensors can be seen in Figure 103. Figure 104 depicts module 8 with the heat pads (red cables on left side of the module) and four type K thermal sensors (green cables on left and right side of the module). Finally, Figure 105 shows the entire 400 V pack right before the start of the test, sitting on a tray on top of the water-filled tank, in which the pack was submerged into after the end of the test. To gain detailed insights into the events during the test, the test was carried out with the top cover of the pack demounted.

Figure 103: Positions of type K thermal sensors and module containing the heat pads. Adopted with adaptations from partner AVL Italia S.r.l.

Figure 104: Module 8 with heat pads around cell in cell group 4.

Figure 105: Battery pack placed on a tray on top of the tank filled with water, ready for the test. Source: Reinova S.p.a.

The plan was to increase the power of the four heat pads in the following stages, with a waiting period between the power levels until the thermal runaway of the heated cell is reached:

- Step 1: Apply 100 W per heat pad → overall $4 \times 100 \text{ W} = 400 \text{ W}$
- maintain until thermal runaway of the cell OR step 1 exceeds 45 min
- Step 2: Apply 130 W per heat pad → overall $4 \times 130 \text{ W} = 520 \text{ W}$
- maintain until thermal runaway of the cell OR step 2 exceeds 45 min
- Step 3: Apply 165 W per heat pad → overall $4 \times 165 \text{ W} = 660 \text{ W}$
- maintain until thermal runaway of the cell OR step 3 exceeds 45 min
- Step 4: Apply 200 W per heat pad → overall $4 \times 200 \text{ W} = 800 \text{ W}$
- maintain until thermal runaway of the cell OR step 4 exceeds 60 min

2.3.2. Execution of the Test

Table 9 shows the actual progress of the thermal runaway test. Since a thermal runaway of the heated cell had already been achieved after step 1 of the planned heat pad-power stages, the heat pads were turned off after the venting of the first cell. After this, eleven additional ventings occurred. Following the last venting, the pack was observed for another hour before submerging it into the water tank.

Table 9: Timetable of events during the thermal propagation test.

Absolute time in hh:mm:ss	Delta t from start of test in hh:mm:ss	Description of event
11:45:01	00:00:00	start of test (start of powering of heatpads (Step 1: 400 W))
12:01:57	00:16:56	venting 1
12:03:38	00:18:37	stop of powering of heatpads
12:04:49	00:19:48	venting 2
12:12:21	00:27:20	venting 3
12:12:57	00:27:56	venting 4
12:13:02	00:28:01	explosion
12:15:18	00:30:17	venting 5
12:16:39	00:31:38	venting 6
12:20:08	00:35:07	venting 7
12:20:38	00:35:37	venting 8
12:23:15	00:38:14	venting 9
12:24:16	00:39:15	venting 10
12:29:57	00:44:56	venting 11
12:33:32	00:48:31	venting 12
13:41:17	01:56:16	submersion of battery pack

Figure 106 shows the venting of a cell. These vented gases then catch fire, as can be seen in Figure 107. Figure 108 depicts the moment of submersion of the battery pack.

Figure 106: Venting of a cell. Source: Reinova S.p.a.

Figure 107: Vented gases catch fire. Source: Reinova S.p.a.

Figure 108: Submersion of the pack after end of test. Source: Reinova S.p.a.

2.3.3. Test Results

Figure 109 and Figure 110 compare the state of the battery pack before and after the thermal runaway test: Module 8 shows clear signs of destruction, whereas the other modules appear to be largely intact.

Figure 109: Comparison of state of pack pre test and post test: State of pack pre test. Source: Reinova S.p.a.

Figure 110: Comparison of state of pack pre test and post test: State of pack post test. Source: Reinova S.p.a.

The diagrams in Figure 111, Figure 112, Figure 113 and Figure 114 show the voltages and temperatures of module 8, which contains the triggered cell, and modules 5, 7 and 9, which are located around module 8. This data is read out by sensors in the pack and transmitted to the

BMS. Each module consists of twelve cells. Two cells form a group and one voltage and one temperature value is transmitted per group at each readout time. The triggered cell is in group 4.

The start time of the test is approximately 2500 seconds in these diagrams. Overall, it can be seen that reliable and regular data transmission no longer takes place for modules 5 and 7 from a time of between 4000 seconds and 4500 seconds. For modules 8 and 9, regular data transmission stops earlier, at a time between 3500 seconds and 4000 seconds.

During the period in which voltage and temperature data are still regularly transmitted, modules 5 and 7 only show a minimal voltage drop, if the voltage drops at all, and a moderate temperature rise to a maximum of around 30 °C for module 5 and 23 °C for module 7.

Module 8 shows the following behavior during the period of regular data transmission: Up to 2585 seconds, the temperature in group 4 rises from 18 °C to 87 °C before the temperature sensor outputs its default value due to the temperature being too high. The voltage in group 4 drops from approx. 4.25 V at the start of the test to approx. 4.20 V at 3524 seconds. In groups 3 and 5 directly next to group 4, the temperature rises from 18 °C to a maximum value of 46 °C and 23 °C respectively. Groups 1, 2 and 6 show a rise in temperature of less than or equal to 2 °C, starting from 17 °C and 18 °C. The voltage drop in all groups apart from group 4 is only minimal, if there is a voltage drop at all.

All groups of module 9 show only very slight voltage dropping, if any, and a rise in temperature of max 2 °C, starting from 17 °C and 18 °C, during the period of regular data transmission.

Figure 115, Figure 116 and Figure 117 show the data recordings of the type K thermocouples that were installed additionally in the pack before the thermal runaway test took place. The positions of these thermocouples can be taken from Figure 103. Figure 115 shows a good correlation between the temperature spikes in module 8 and the times of venting, see Table 9. Whilst ignoring the questionable spikes in red around 12:15:00, 12:21:00 and 12:23:00, it can be seen that the temperatures rise slowly from the beginning until the time of the first vent at 12:01:57, when temperatures begin to rise and fall rapidly, reaching a maximum of around 500 °C, before slowly decreasing again after the last vent at 12:33:32.

Figure 116 shows the data from the type K thermocouples installed in module 9, right next to module 8. The ventings from venting 3 onwards at 12:12:21 seem to have a great impact temperaturewise on module 9. Since temperatures reach a maximum of 525 °C, it must be assumed that some of the ventings were cells of module 9.

Figure 117 shows that module 5 saw a maximum temperature of ca. 77 °C during the test and module 7 saw a maximum temperature of 40 °C during the test. No temperature spikes are visible for module 5 and 7. The temperature sensor located at the JBOX on the other hand saw a rise in temperature of up to 173 °C, since it was located very close to module 8.

Figure 111: Voltage and temperature values of module 5 during the test - derived from the battery pack's BMS.

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Figure 112: Voltage and temperature values of module 7 during the test - derived from the battery pack's BMS.

Figure 113: Voltage and temperature values of module 8 during the test - derived from the battery pack's BMS.

Figure 114: Voltage and temperature values of module 9 during the test - derived from the battery pack's BMS.

Figure 115: Temperature values at module 8 during the test - derived from additionally installed type K thermal sensors.

Figure 116: Temperature values at module 9 during the test - derived from additionally installed type K thermal sensors.

Figure 117: Temperature values at modules 5, 7 and the JBOX during the test - derived from additionally installed type K thermal sensors.

Overall, it can be assumed that the thermal insulation between the individual cells slows thermal propagation, as the venting extends over a large period of time. It should also be noted that the distance between the individual modules protected all modules, except module 9, from extremely high temperatures and thermal runaways of their own cells. However, these statements only apply to thermal runaways with the lid of the pack removed. If the pack's lid is closed and a thermal runaway of a cell occurs, a different temperature distribution in the pack must be assumed.

3. AI-driven battery state prediction process and results

3.1. Overview of the Methodology

The AI-driven battery state prediction process is realized with the use of the data-driven Digital Twin of Electric Vehicle (EV) Li-Ion battery, which embeds AI and ML algorithms in order to support several and dynamic predictive analytics processes to address the challenges of adaptability, modularity and precision in battery health and performance prediction, reported in the Deliverable D4.1: "Models and estimation algorithm description". The Digital Twin incorporates AI models in order to compute SOC estimation, provide remote diagnosis based on early failure detection, predict upcoming internal battery failures on several components, and prevent a fatal failure. In addition, it includes data preprocessing techniques and methods (e.g. for automated data cleansing and formatting) that ensure the quality and the value of the data to be used as input by the AI based models and therefore, they facilitate AI model development and training.

In order to apply the AI and ML algorithms to the testing procedures, we applied the methodology presented in **Error! No se encuentra el origen de la referencia.**⁸, following a modular approach and enabling users to plug in different models, algorithms, and preprocessing techniques to suit specific datasets or applications. The methodology is structured around three core components. The first component involves the Configuration for battery state prediction, where the foundational parameters, steps, and processes that govern each experimental setup are meticulously defined. The second component delves into the Process specific to battery state predictive analytics. This stage encompasses the methodologies employed for data ingestion, preprocessing, and feature engineering, along with the integration of different predictive models tailored to the complexities of battery behavior. The third component centers on the Prediction of the defined battery state, which involves applying and validating predictive models to estimate battery state indicators (e.g. SOC). This phase consolidates the methodology's outputs, emphasizing the accuracy and the scalability of these battery states. The methodology's versatility is also underscored by its ability to accommodate diverse use cases, particularly through the integration of different datasets tailored to the pipelines for SOC and RUL prediction. Each dataset reflects distinct characteristics, such as variations in operational conditions, battery chemistry and degradation profiles. By leveraging datasets with varying attributes, the framework not only enhances its predictive accuracy but also demonstrates its capacity to adjust to a broad spectrum of battery data profiles.

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Figure 118: The methodology for Li-ion batteries battery states prediction.

3.2. Application of the Methodology and Results

In this case, we have conducted several implementations of this methodology for SOC prediction using the test data which recorded and collected in the context of the MARBEL project. To begin with, the first step of this pipeline, after the configuration of several parameters, is Data Collection, which encompasses the collection of data from a variety of data sources. This process enables the integration of discrepant datasets into the predictive analytics pipeline by considering the type of the specific data source and the possible metadata that derive. This step is essential for data management procedures since it is the first step in making data accessible and usable for analytics and in parallel creating a comprehensive and cohesive foundation for analytics. In this phase, we analysed various datasets generated during the cycling process, which were captured using different equipment under varying cycling conditions.

An additional step to our analysis refers to the Data Harmonization process which refers to the organization and unification of the data in a suitable way for our analysis. This process refers to unification of datasets from different data sources but also different datasets from the same source. Specifically, several variables are adjusted to the battery data model, which has been reported in the Deliverable D4.1: “Models and estimation algorithm description”.

In the context of the methodology, we performed an Exploratory Data Analysis (EDA) of several variables in order to examine features related to the variables of voltage, current, charge capacity, discharge capacity, and temperature, such as the maximum and the minimum value of these parameters through time. An indicative example of the outcomes of this process is shown in Figure 119.

Figure 119: EDA of several variables of a dataset (a: capacity, b: charge capacity, c: discharge capacity, d: current, e: voltage, f: temperature).

Then, the Data Preprocessing, which refers to all the required data cleaning, handling, structuring and validating needs that prepare the data and facilitate the upcoming analysis, is executed. Data cleaning was necessary due to the outliers in the beginning of the battery’s cycling. Moreover, in several datasets, the battery’s capacity calculation was necessary since this feature was not recorded directly through the battery’s cycling process. In some other cases, the construction of the feature of cycle number was required.

The last component of the methodology is assigned to the Battery State Prediction referring to the implementation of the pipeline and its evaluation as well as the collection and comparison of the evaluation metrics. All the above procedures are correlated with the selected battery state through the initial configuration, considering all the outlined dimensions. We have applied many different pipelines by a unique combination of dataset, characterized by specific cycling conditions, ML model and input variables. Thus, for the last step of the pipeline, it was necessary to define several parameters such as the ML model, the input features, as well as the training and testing set for the corresponding procedures.

The final outcome is the performance of the ML pipeline using appropriate evaluation metrics. For example, Figure 120 depicts the actual and predicted values for the pipeline applying the Linear Regression model, while Figure 121 depicts the actual and predicted values for the pipeline applying the Feed Forward Neural Network. Table 10 presents the results from the optimal pipelines for the dataset at hand. The high accuracy of the ML pipelines validates their high performance; however, it should be considered that the existing data has a specific range of lifetimes and as a result they present a smooth operation of the battery without noticeable degradation between the consecutive cycles. For more extensive experiments, it is expected that the values of these metrics will be lower, but still of great value, as the experiments presented in the Deliverable D4.1: “Models and estimation algorithm description” prove. Another notice has to do with the fact that complex ML pipelines, that are computationally costly, are not necessary in this case.

Figure 120: The actual and predicted values for the pipeline applying the Linear Regression model.

Figure 121: The actual and predicted values for the pipeline applying the Feed Forward Neural Network.

Table 10: Performance metrics of the optimal pipelines.

Dataset's characteristics	Features	Model	RMSE (SOC %)	Accuracy (R ²) (%)
AmbTemp: 10oC Life: 318 cycles	V, I, C, T	LR	0.025	99.89
AmbTemp: 23oC Life: 317 cycles	V, I, C, T	SVR	7.07	95.18
AmbTemp: 23oC Life: 148 cycles	V, T, V _{mean} , I _{mean}	FFNN	4.51	97.67
AmbTemp: 10oC Life: 153 cycles	V, T, V _{mean} , I _{mean}	AutoML	5.37	96.27

4. AI-driven SOC estimation with an integrated ECM-ML approach

4.1. Overview of the Methodology

We integrated into the Equivalent Circuit Model (ECM) to Machine Learning methods in order to estimate the State of Charge (SOC) of the battery. To do this, we used Reinforcement Learning (RL), which is an interdisciplinary area of Machine Learning and focuses on how an agent takes actions in a dynamic environment with the purpose of achieving the optimal reward signal [2].

In general, through the RL method, an agent is trained to interact with the environment and look for rewards regarding its actions [2]. In this context, the implemented RL environment trains an agent that controls the parameters of the ECM model to keep the model response matching the observations. Without any knowledge of the structure or the nature of the ECM model, the agent examines a great variety of possible responses of the system and concludes to good and bad rewards.

So, in this case, the reward signal is declared through this Reward Function and the actions of the agent are presented through the calibration of the parameters of the ECM model. Furthermore, a Neural Network has been trained to make optimal predictions of the parameters of the ECM using the Reward Function of RL and the parameters calibration process. Through this process, the SOC is estimated and evaluated.

The training process is depicted in Figure 122: The training process of the integrated ECM and RL approach for SOC prediction. During the training process, the selected measurements (observations) of the dataset are given as input to the Neural Network and thus, it estimates the parameters (actions) of the ECM model. In parallel, the same measurements are given as input to the ECM. In the next step, the ECM uses the input measurements and the input parameters to estimate the SOC. Then, the estimated SOC and the calculated SOC based on the dataset are the inputs to the Reward Function. The result of the Reward Function is used by the Reinforcement Learning algorithm to calibrate the Neural Network and minimize the estimation error. The Reward function is the main component of the RL environment, which has been proven to be effective in finding optimal control policies for nonlinear systems with dynamic behavior that have a degree of uncertainty. Finally, the outcome of the Reward function is given as input to the Neural Network so that the model is calibrated, and its parameters take the optimal value. After the training process, the Neural Network has learned the optimal parameters of the ECM and by applying a new dataset, the predicted SOC is generated through this optimum parameterized ECM.

Figure 122: The training process of the integrated ECM and RL approach for SOC prediction.

4.2. Dataset and Training Process

To implement this integrated ECM-RL approach for SOC estimation, there is the need for datasets about Li-Ion batteries that have been charged/discharged till failure using fast charging. Due to the cells delay in MARBEL, it was not possible to collect a sufficient dataset for validating this approach. Therefore, we used an open dataset meeting these requirements. The datasets used (Severson et al., 2019) consist of 124 commercial lithium-ion batteries which have been charged/discharged till failure using fast charging. These lithium-ion cells were cycled in horizontal cylindrical fixtures on a 48-channel Arbin LBT potentiostat in a forced convection temperature chamber set to 30 °C. The cells have a nominal capacity of 1.1 Ah and a nominal voltage of 3.3 V. There are also temperature measurements that have been performed by a Type T thermocouple. It should be considered that because of the nature of the experiment the temperature measurements could exhibit reduced accuracy since the thermal contact between the thermocouple and the cell may vary or the thermocouple could lose contact during some cycles. The datasets are divided into three different groups each consisting of about 48 cells. Each group has a separate date denoting when the tests started. Below, we present the information related to the experiments corresponding to each group.

Measurement Group 1

1. All cells were cycled with one-step or two-step charging policies. The charging time varies from ~8 to 13.3 minutes (0-80% SOC). There are generally two cells tested per policy, with the exception of 3.6C (80%).
2. 1 minute and 1 second rests were placed after reaching 80% SOC during charging and after discharging, respectively.
3. We cycle to 80% of nominal capacity (0.88 Ah).
4. An initial C/10 cycle was performed in the beginning of each test.
5. The cutoff currents for the constant-voltage steps were C/50 for both charge and discharge.
6. The pulse width of the IR test is 30 ms.

Measurement Group 2

1. All cells were cycled with one-step or two-step charging policies. The charging time is fixed at 10 minutes (0-80% SOC). There is generally only one cell tested per policy, with the exception of 4.8C(80%) (three cells).
2. We resumed 5 cells from the 2017-05-12 batch that didn't complete yet - 3.6C and 4.0C.
3. We cycle to 75% of nominal capacity (0.88 Ah).
4. 5 minute rests were placed both after reaching 80% SOC during charging and after discharging.
5. An initial C/10 cycle was performed in the beginning of each test.
6. The cutoff currents for the constant-voltage steps were C/50 for both charge and discharge.
7. The pulse width of the IR test is 30 ms.

Measurement Group 3

1. All cells were cycled with two-step charging policies. The charging time fixed at 10 minutes (0-80% SOC). We test multiple cells per policy (3-8x per policy).
2. We cycle to 80% of nominal capacity (0.88 Ah).
3. Four 5-second rests were placed after reaching 80% SOC during charging, after the IR test, before discharging, and after discharging.
4. A final C/10 cycle was performed at 80% of nominal capacity.
5. The cutoff currents for the constant-voltage steps were C/20 for both charge and discharge.
6. The pulse width of the IR test is 33 ms.

Figure 123 depicts a plot of the dataset for 7 consecutive cycles each belonging to a different dataset. With blue we have the current that is applied to or drawn from the battery (depending if we are currently charging or discharging). Here positive currents denote that the battery is charging. With orange we have the voltage as measured in the battery terminals. With green we have the real SOC as measured in the experiment (ranges from 0 to 1). As we can see, we have different load conditions that are exerted on the battery depending on the experiment selected, especially during the charging stage where different charging profiles have been implemented. Figure 124 depicts the plot of temperature for the same experiments. The graph is in Kelvin degrees and we can see that more or less the temperature is within the range of 30 - 40 degrees Celsius. We can also see that the temperature is rising as the experiments progress.

Figure 123: Battery's Current, Voltage and SOC.

Figure 124: Battery's Temperature.

Figure 125 presents two measurement cycles from different datasets for a more detailed look. As we can see the cycles have a constant discharge current of about 4.4 A and a charging stage with varying currents with a maximum of about 6.6 A. We can see that the terminal voltage of the battery also changes, but as expected, much less than the current in the two cycles. Within each cycle the voltage drops or increases with respect to its SOC (denoting the voltage drop as a battery depletes). The SOC of each cycle also has differences between the cycles if plotted against each other but overall the curve appears similar.

Figure 125: Battery's Current, Voltage and State of Charge (1 Cycle).

For the training process, we modelled the problem in terms of RL; therefore, we defined the Action Space and the Observation Space as follows.

- **Action Space:** The action space is the range of values that can be proposed by the Actor of the RL algorithm (the physical system's parameters in our case). This needs to be selected using a reasonable range of values because if care is not taken we could exclude the optimal solutions altogether as we constraint the algorithm not to search in those ranges. On the other hand, if the range is too big, we can increase the training time needlessly as the RL algorithm will evaluate parameters that are not realistic for our system thus wasting processing cycles. Typical range of parameters include 0.001Ω to 0.5Ω for the resistors and 500 F to 10000 F for capacitors. The parameters for the SOC polynomial range from a little below zero to around 10.
- **Observation Space:** The observation space is in turn the range of values the inputs to the SAC algorithm are going to take (in essence the value domain). These ranges are defined

by the datasets available and are the ranges of the inputs that have been measured during the experiments. So to set the observation space we look at those ranges in the dataset (and we also make the range slightly bigger to have some extra room). In our case the voltage is between 1.8V - 3.8V, current is between -5.0A and 7.0A and temperature between 300°K and 315°K.

4.3. Results

Two different main models have been validated. The base battery model is a 2nd Order ECM which provides a good tradeoff between model complexity and accuracy capturing the main battery dynamics such as battery hysteresis and polarization with an adequate approximation. The difference between the use cases is the approximation used for the modeling of the State of Charge of the battery which is combined with the 2nd Order ECM to calculate the charge and discharge of a Li-ion battery. For the State of Charge two approximations have been considered. The first is a linear approximation of the V_{oc} and SOC and the second is a cubic approximation of the V_{oc} and SOC that also includes a linear term to take into account the battery's temperature.

4.3.1. 2nd Order ECM - Linear SOC Approximation

This model uses a 2nd Order ECM and a linear approximation with respect to SOC and temperature. Figure 126 depicts the output of the model for 7 consecutive charge and discharge cycles of a Li-ion battery. The model can in general achieve a good approximation of the state of charge with the exception of the top part of the cycle where it has a flatter output.

Figure 126: Model 1 - State of Charge Results.

Figure 127 depicts the output of the neural network. This is a selection from all the parameters that are provided by the model (for example also the resistances and capacitances of the model are provided). We observe that the model actively changes the parameters capturing the non-linear behavior of the system. Figure 128 provides the measured parameters V and I that are used as an input to the circuit and the open circuit voltage V_{oc} which is an intermediate variable in the system and the output of the 2nd order ECM.

Figure 127: Model 1 - Neural Network Parameters.

Figure 128: Model 1 - ECM Inputs and Outputs.

4.3.2. 2nd Order ECM - Cubic SOC Approximation - Model 1

This is the second model that has been evaluated and the SOC results are depicted in Figure 129. This is also using a 2nd Order ECM for the battery, but it also uses a cubic approximation for the SOC of the battery as well as a linear term for the temperature. This model also has a good overall approximation of the SOC although we can observe some flatter regions on the top of each charge cycle. The error of those flat regions is reduced with respect to the linear model presented above.

Figure 129: Model 2 - State of Charge Results.

Figure 130 and Figure 131 present a selection of the parameters of the output of the neural network. We can see here that since the approximation is cubic we have two more parameters that have been introduced to represent the coefficients for the square and cubic terms of the equation. We also present the graph of the physical measurements and ECM output (V_{oc}).

Figure 130: Model 2 - Neural Network Parameters.

Figure 131: Model 2 - ECM Inputs and Outputs.

4.3.3. 2nd Order ECM - Cubic SOC Approximation - Model 2

This model is identical with the model of the previous section. It uses a 2nd order ECM, a cubic approximation for SOC as well as a linear term for modeling the battery temperature. The difference between the two models is that they have been trained independently for similar times with the same methodology and on the same datasets to investigate the results. Its results are shown in Figure 132. As we can see, the output of the whole model also achieves a reasonable approximation of the real SOC but is a bit different from the one of the previous one mostly in the top regions of the curve where the calculated output does not have as flat a response as before. As a trade off we can observe that there are some deviations in lower regions of the curve. In general with these comparisons we want to present that using the same methodology can produce slightly different models as the neural network that is produced by the learning process can converge to different values depending on the nature of the functions and local minima that it can find. In any case those models both approximate the SOC with similar accuracy so there are not big deviations in the total errors.

Figure 132: Model 3 - State of Charge Results.

Figure 133 presents the parameters as are outputted from the NN and Figure 134 for the output of the ECM model along with the real parameters V and I as measured in the real battery. It is worth noting here that some visible differences occur between these models that lead to similar approximations of the SOC though. This makes evident the different minima that this approach can converge to, something that is expected to be amplified the more complex a model gets.

Figure 133: Model 3 - Neural Network Parameters.

Figure 134: Model 3 - ECM Inputs and Outputs.

4.3.4. 2nd Order ECM - Cubic SOC Approximation - Filter

All the above models present an acceptable approximation of the state of charge for different applications and alone or maybe with some minor tweaking can be used with acceptable accuracy. One step further can be to add one more stage to the whole model which is the filtering of the output. This does not require any changes to the ECM model or the NN which can be used as is. The idea here is that the 2nd Order ECM model, although a system of linear differential equations, can present some discontinuities at times when coupled with the NN. The reason is that since the NN changes the parameters of the model in real time, big changes will affect the internal behavior of the model instantly producing jumps and overshooting. This is slightly counteracted by the fact that the ECM model includes two capacitors that could slightly filter these changes as a side effect but they cannot do this for the SOC model that is also affected by the NN and also this is not their main function as they only need to model the internal behavior of the battery correctly.

Thus a simple filter has been added to the output of the model to investigate if the behavior will improve. Any filter could be used with different cut off frequencies but here a simple moving average has been used. This filter has three effects on the model output. Firstly it smoothens the output depending on the cut off frequency (or number of samples in the case of the moving average) that has been selected. As a byproduct of the filtering, which is affected by our previous selection, the output amplitude is reduced and a time lag is also introduced. The two effects are not desirable so special steps are taken so they can be compensated.

In this case we present the final model that produced the best results. This is a model identical to the 2nd Order ECMs with Cubic SOC approximation (discussed in the previous two sections) but also the proposed filtering has been added in the output. Both cubic models can produce similar results so any one of them can be selected (so the neural network that has been used is from one of the models that has been presented above and not a newly trained one).

Figure 135, Figure 136, and Figure 137 present the output of the model. We can see that the output is much smoother and it produces a better overall fit. Some small peaks exist at the highest point that is a remnant of the overshooting of the normal output but overall there are much smaller spikes in the graph. This could be expected as the state of charge of a battery is expected to change slowly in most normal scenarios. The two graphs for the NN estimated parameters as well as the ECM inputs and outputs are also given.

Figure 135: Model 4 - State of Charge Results.

Figure 136: Model 4 - Neural Network Parameters.

Figure 137: Model 4 - ECM Inputs and Outputs.

4.3.5. Overview of Results

Overall, the physical model already captures part of the dynamics which makes it easier for the RL algorithm to converge to a solution and improves accuracy. The NN trained by the RL can drive the model to an optimal state by introducing non-linear behavior by changing its parameters while leaving the model to capture faster dynamics that could be harder to capture with a data driven approach. In general from the results presented above the accuracy of estimation has low error even for the simpler models. Between the models we can observe some improvements, which is desirable, but depending on the application these improvements may not necessarily be needed and a simpler model could provide adequate accuracy. Indeed even the worst performing model which is linear does achieve low error metrics by itself. The biggest inaccuracies of these models lie mostly in specific regions (mostly on the top and bottom regions of the state of charge curve).

Lastly we present the error metrics of all the models together (Table 11). As we described above all models use the same 2nd Order ECM as the underlying battery model and have been trained on the same datasets for similar time. All models also include the temperature as a linear term in the SOC estimation. The difference lies in the order of the SOC model with respect to the SOC variable itself. We can see that the linear model with respect to SOC achieves the lower accuracy (although still good in absolute terms). Then we have the two Cubic models that have been separately trained which provide an increase in the overall accuracy with respect to the linear model and similar performance with respect to each other. The final model is the Cubic model that has a filter applied to its output as described above with no alterations to the internal behavior of the model either the ECM or the NN which also provides an improved performance with respect to all the previous models.

Table 11: Comparison of Results

Error Metrics				
	<i>2nd Order ECM + Linear SOC</i>	<i>2nd Order ECM + Cubic SOC 1</i>	<i>2nd Order ECM + Cubic SOC 2</i>	<i>2nd Order ECM + Cubic SOC + Filter</i>
RMSE	5.66%	4.95%	4.94%	4.49%
MAE	3.66%	3.17%	3.41%	2.94%
R-Squared	0.976	0.982	0.982	0.985

5. Conclusion

In this deliverable, the performed test procedures and the results have been explained and evaluated. Starting from cell level, it has been investigated how the cells behave and degrade under different operating conditions. Thus, they have been cycled at three different temperatures and two different C-rates, which revealed a very moderate degradation behavior under the applied conditions. In addition, the characterization tests revealed a relatively low internal resistance.

Before fully assembled modules have been available in the project, a conceptual cooling design test setup has been built to attach the cells to cooling components of the prevailing cooling design at the time and to mimic a module-like structure for thermal performance measurements. This setup has been used to develop a methodology for virtual development of thermal management systems as well as for a continuous WLTC cycling combined with fast charging phases, to account for real driving conditions. Additionally, this setup allowed to pretension the cells and continuously monitor the force over the number of cycles, to investigate the impact of potentially changing stack-pressure conditions. The results showed a low degradation in terms of capacity fade, while the overall pretension force did not considerably increase. In addition, the conceptual cooling design allowed for applying the high fast charge current of 2C, while temperatures remained in a very decent range.

As soon as the modules were available, tests have been performed to validate their electrical behavior as well as the communications linked to the BMS. To account for the cooling concept, that is available in the full pack, a reduced-size cooling plate setup has been assembled around the cell to validate the final cooling design before the full pack was available. Although the BMS communications posed some problems and thus prevented from applying a full cycle to the module, it could be shown that the cooling system has a considerable impact on the thermal conditioning of the modules. This was possible by connecting three modules in series, to build a “mini-pack”. With this approach, the interconnection of the BMS communications has been evaluated. Since two of the three modules have not been actively cooled, the cooling setup could be compared in terms of thermal performance. The modules were moreover used for cybersecurity-related experiments, where it could be shown that the Bluetooth channel might cause some risks in the current state, but a definitive evaluation could not be drawn due to a lack of experimental data.

A vibration test performed at full (400 V) pack level revealed some potential issues with the connection methods within the BMS communications as well as mechanical fixation topics inside the battery pack, highlighting the importance of such a test to account for in-field conditions. The results have already been fed back to the respective entities, to take a maximum out of the test.

Abusive tests done at cell, module and pack level demonstrated the behavior of the DUTs under abnormal conditions and weak points. While at cell and pack level certain abusive experiments show less “spectacular” reactions, there are potentially dangerous situations and conditions that lead to a thermal runaway of the cells. A thermal runaway test, initiated by overheating of a cell in the middle of a module, did show however that the design of the MARBEL pack helps to extend the duration between a potential thermal propagation from one cell to another. In fact, only the module that has actively been overheated went into a thermal runaway, whereas even the inner-module propagation did take quite a time.

The results obtained from the tests were moreover used with sophisticated AI-based methodologies to further improve the gained insights and knowledge about the system. Besides an AI-based battery state prediction, a novel approach to combine ECM and machine learning models for SOC prediction has been investigated (and still is). This will not only improve the

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evaluation quality but will also contribute to an overall improvement of the test procedures as a whole.

As a matter of fact, the executed experiments and the gained results reflect the tremendous work and the passion invested by the MARBEL consortium into the developed system: a versatile, performant and next-generation battery pack paving the way for future developments and improvements.

6. REFERENCES

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